

ADMINISTRATIVE EMPOWERMENT VIS A VIS SCHOOL HEAD'S DECISION MAKING: THE CASE OF MBHTE-SULU, BARMM, PHILIPPINES

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ABSTRACT

Since decision making plays a very significant role in managing a school institution, this study therefore sought to determine the administrative empowerment of school heads in selected schools in MBHTE-Sulu, BARMM in terms of school, head's Decision Making. Further, this investigation used descriptive mixed method to find out the level of school head's empowerment. School head and teachers from the different elementary schools were chosen as respondents of the study. In like manner, Self-made questionnaire and interview were used in gathering the data. Meanwhile, frequency counts, mean, t-test and ANOVA were used in the interpretation of data. Meanwhile, the majority of the school heads were male, aged from 56-65, most of them were with masteral degree and have been rendering services from 21-30 years.. The school heads were rated "highly empowered" in terms of decision making, Further, there was no significant difference between male and female on their perspective on the areas of administrative empowerment. Also, there was a significant difference on the perception of the respondents in terms of age. Meanwhile, there was no significant difference on administrative empowerment in decision making in terms of educational qualification and length of services. Moreover, there was a significant difference between the perception of the administrators and the teachers as to decision making.

Keywords: *Administrator, Empowerment, Administrative Empowerment, Decision Making, BARMM*

INTRODUCTION

In the 21st century educational landscape, school principals play a pivotal role in improving learning and attaining educational outcomes which lead them to work under strenuous condition to deal with multifaceted transformational issues (Bogler & Nir : 2012; Bateman : 2010 ; & Block :2023). Administrators experience great difficulty in coping with numerous changes, partly because they are prepared for their leadership position, or simply lack of necessary skills, knowledge and attitudes to lead and manage schools effectively and efficiently. Fundamentally, administrators should be empowered to effectively deal with challenges facing them in this fast-changing techno-era (Abdurahman:2023).

School administrators in Pangutaran District have to cope with litany of changes vis-a-vis the ever-evolving educational dynamism in the playing field. Hence empowerment in decision-making is a must but necessary. In this context, this investigation is delving deeper on how the school administrators of selected elementary schools in the said district have manifest their roles and responsibilities in this modern era.

This study is based on the theory of Ifani (2011) on schools' empowerment issues over the last three decades. She stressed that empowerment is a means to include the team in decision-making. While Terry (2000) asserted that the principal is the central figure in the creation of empowered schools. Hence, Amundsen & Martinsen (2014) and Abdurahman & Omar (2021) believed that empowering leadership is the ability to share power, give freedom and autonomy, delegate responsibility to subordinates that entails enhancing the meaningfulness of work, fostering participation and expressing confidence in decision-making.

The school administrators in the Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education (MBHTE) in the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (BARMM) has long been facing dilemma in school the mainstream of school governance. According to Abdurahman (2023) that the school heads have seemingly denied of their rights over major decisions for the improvement of their respective schools. They felt there exist a highly centralized form of governance in the higher echelon of the government bureaucratic setting specifically in school affairs.

Moreover, involvement of school principals in planning instructional programs and activities would make them cooperate with the administration in achieving the desired educational goals. However, the extent and level of principal's empowerment in decision-making is affected by their socio-demographic and academic factors.

In this investigation, the researchers explored the administrative empowerment of school heads in terms of decision-making in Pangutaran District MBHTE-Sulu. This hopes to shed light on importance of promoting a culture of professional development that will prepare principals to confront education challenges and obstacles brought about by the dynamics of the 21st century education landscape.

Research Problems

This study sought to determine the administrative empowerment of school heads in Selected Public Elementary Schools in Pangutaran District. Specifically, it answers the following research questions:

1. What is the profile of the school heads in Pangutaran District in the context of gender, age, length of service and educational qualifications?
2. What is the level of administrative empowerment in decision-making at the selected public elementary school administrators in Pangutaran District, MBHTE-Sulu?
3. Is there any significant difference in school administrators' empowerment in decision-making when grouped according to administrators' personal profile with respect to gender, age, length of service and educational qualification?

METHODOLOGY

This section presents the research methodology and procedure used in the study. It contains the research locale, sampling procedure, research instrument, and statistical treatment of data.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in Pangutaran municipality specifically on the selected Public Elementary Schools in Pangutaran District, MBHTE-Sulu of Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (BARMM), Southern Philippines. The study comprised 30 elementary schools with 25 school principals; five officer's in-charge; and 180 faculty members. While Pangutaran is an island situated about 30 miles north of mainland Sulu. Composed of 16 Barangays with hardworking and hospitable constituents, said municipality is considered one of the peaceful areas in the Province of Sulu.

Sampling Procedure

This is the process of selecting number of individuals from the population such that the selected group contains elements representative of the characteristics found in the entire group called a sample (Kothari :2004), consequently samples can be selected by a sampling design.

The respondents of the study were the twenty (20) school heads and twenty (20) teachers purposively selected from 30 public elementary schools in Pangutaran District, Pangutaran, Sulu. The criteria in selecting the respondents were: (1) school heads and teachers whose residents are in mainland Pangutaran; (2) the school or station where they are assigned or working with; and (3) the availability of their time or the easiest to deal with.

Research Instruments

The main source of the data in this study was the result of the researchers-made-checklist questionnaires. Its reliability was measured using Cronbach's Alpha method to establish correlation between items and questionnaire. This was validated by three panel of experts from *MSU-Sulu Graduate School* namely; *Prof. Melchor B. Ynawat; Prof. Allen I. Talikan; and Prof. Nurminie Supian-Udjah,*

There were two components of the checklist questionnaire. Part I inquires the profile of the respondents with respect to their gender, age, educational qualification and length of service.; and part II- inquires their perceptions on specific questions leading to determine the level of perceptions on administrators' empowerment in in terms of decision-making situation public school in Pangutaran District, Division of Sulu. The following is the rating scale: 5- Too highly empowered; 4- Highly empowered; 3- Moderately empowered; 2- Less empowered; and 1- Not empowered at all.

The questionnaire was launched to 40 respondents of which 20 were school administrators and 20 teachers. The launching of the questionnaires was personally distributed to the selected school administrators and selected teachers. The respondents were given a time to answer the questionnaire for one week.

The researchers retrieved the questionnaire after duly accomplished by the selected school administrators and selected teachers as respondents. As soon as the questionnaire was collected, the researchers tallied the responses in the SPSS program and further computed to answer the research questions.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The frequency and percentage were used to determine the demographic profile of the school administrators on selected schools in Pangutaran District with respect to their gender, age, length of service and educational qualifications. While mean was employed to determine the level of empowerment in decision-making, formulation and implementation of school policies, and instructional planning. T-test and one-way analysis of variance were utilized to determine the significant difference on the level of administrative empowerment of school heads according to their personal profile. T-test was also used to analyze the difference on the level of school head's administrative empowerment as rated by both the school heads themselves and the teachers.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study aimed at exploring the administrative empowerment of school heads in selected public elementary schools in Pangutaran District, Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education (MBHTE-Sulu) , Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (BARMM), Philippines. This study specifically investigates the profile of the respondents and the perception of both the school heads and the selected elementary school teachers on the administrative decision making of the school administrators. This also include how do these perceptions varies in the context of gender, age, length of service and educational qualification. Further, this study was delimited to 20 selected school administrators and 20 selected elementary school teachers. Other variables of administrative empowerment such as instructional planning and formulation of school

policies were not included in the investigation. However, distance from island schools to other schools was the prominent constraints in the conduct of the study.

RESULTS

This section presents the findings of the study. This includes the profile of the school heads of Pangutaran District; their administrative empowerment in terms of decision making; differences according to their profile in the context of their gender, age, length of service and educational qualification; and the differences on administrative decision making as perceived by the teachers and the administrators themselves.

A. Profile of the School Heads

Table 1 presents the profile of the school heads in Pangutaran District, MBHTE-Sulu. The following distribution were found. As to gender, Majority 55% were male; In terms Age, majority 35% were ranged from 56-65 years old. As to length of service, majority 40% have 31-40 years of teaching experience; and as to educational Qualification, Majority 50% have finished masteral degree.

Table 1: Profile of the School Heads in Pangutaran District

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	11	55
Female	9	45
Age		
25-35 years old	2	10
36-45 years old	6	30
46-55 years old	5	25
56-65 years old	7	35
Length of Service		
10 years below	2	10
11-20 years	6	30
21-30 years	8	40
31-40 years	4	20
41 years and above	0	0
Educational Qualifications		
Bachelor's Degree	0	0
With Master's Units	3	15
Master's Degree	10	50
With Doctoral Units	4	20
Doctoral Degree	3	15

B. Administrative Empowerment in Terms of Decision-Making as Rated by Teachers

Table 2 presents the administrative empowerment in terms of decision making as rated by the elementary school teachers. As such, the overall mean is 4.11 with a verbal description of highly empowered. Whereas, the highest individual mean is 4.60 and the lowest is 3.65.

Table 2: Administrators Empowerment in Terms of Decision Making as Rated by Teachers

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Description
1. I make decision with the consent and knowledge of my superior.	4.20	Highly Empowered
2. I make decision that suit to my teachers.	4.35	Highly Empowered
3. I make decisions in a logical and systematic way.	4.10	Highly Empowered
4. When making decisions, I consider various options in terms of a specific goal.	4.25	Highly Empowered
5. I make decision to ensure its proper execution.	4.05	Highly Empowered
6. When making decisions, I rely upon my instincts.	3.75	Highly Empowered
7. When making decision, I rely on my intuition.	3.65	Highly Empowered
8. When I make decision, I make sure that it is rational.	4.20	Highly Empowered
9. I seek the advice of other people in making an important decisions.	4.10	Highly Empowered
10. When I am under pressure, I will not decide.	3.80	Highly Empowered
11. I make decision for the development of the school.	4.60	Too highly empowered
12. I consider various factors in making decision.	4.20	Highly Empowered
13. I avoid making important decisions until the pressure is on.	4.00	Highly Empowered
14. I make good and timely decisions, and ensure that they are executed.	4.10	Highly Empowered
15. I make decision based on reliable sources.	4.25	Highly Empowered
Overall Mean	4.11	Highly Empowered

C. Administrators Empowerment in Terms of Decision Making as Rated by Administrators themselves

Table 3 highlights the administrative empowerment in terms of decision making as rated by the elementary school administrators themselves. It was found, the overall mean is 4.15 with a verbal description of highly empowered. While the highest individual mean is 4.65 and the lowest is 3.70.

Table 3: Administrators Empowerment in Terms of Decision Making as Rated by Administrators themselves

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Description
1.1 I make decision with the consent and knowledge of my superior.	4.30	Highly Empowered
1.2 I make decision that suit to my teachers.	4.50	Highly Empowered
1.3 I make decisions in a logical and systematic way.	4.25	Highly Empowered
1.4 When making decisions, I consider various options in terms of a specific goal.	4.10	Highly Empowered
1.5.I make decision to ensure its proper execution.	4.25	Highly Empowered
1.6 When making decisions, I rely upon my instincts.	3.70	Highly Empowered
1.7 When making decision, I rely on my intuition.	3.75	Highly Empowered
1.8 When I make decision, I make sure that it is rational.	4.10	Highly Empowered
1.9 I seek the advice of other people in making an important decisions.	4.00	Highly Empowered
1.10 When I am under pressure, I will not decide.	3.90	Highly Empowered
1.11 I make decision for the development of the school.	4.65	Too highly empowered
1.12 I consider various factors in making decision.	4.20	Highly Empowered
1.13 I avoid making important decisions until the pressure is on.	3.95	Highly Empowered
1.14 I make good and timely decisions, and ensure that they are executed.	4.00	Highly Empowered
1.15 I make decision based on	4.55	Highly Empowered

reliable sources.		
Average Mean	4.15	Highly Empowered

D. Administrative Empowerment in Terms of Decision-Making as Rated by Administrators and Teachers

Table 4 states the administrative empowerment in terms of decision making as rated by the administrators themselves and elementary school teachers. The following distributions were found: the overall mean is 4.13 with a verbal description of highly empowered. Whereas, the highest individual mean is 4.63 and the lowest is 3.70.

Table 4 : Administrators Empowerment in Terms of Decision Making as Rated by Administrators and Teachers

INDICATORS	Administrator's Rating	Teacher's Rating	Mean	Verbal Description
1. DECISION-MAKING				
1.1 I make decision with the consent and knowledge of my superior.	4.30	4.20	4.25	Highly Empowered
1.2 I make decision that suit to my teachers.	4.50	4.35	4.43	Highly Empowered
1.3 I make decisions in a logical and systematic way.	4.25	4.10	4.18	Highly Empowered
1.4 When making decisions, I consider various options in terms of a specific goal.	4.10	4.25	4.18	Highly Empowered
1.5.I make decision to ensure its proper execution.	4.25	4.05	4.15	Highly Empowered
1.6 When making decisions, I rely upon my instincts.	3.70	3.75	3.73	Highly Empowered
1.7 When making decision, I rely on my intuition.	3.75	3.65	3.70	Highly Empowered
1.8 When I make decision, I make sure that it is rational.	4.10	4.20	4.15	Highly Empowered
1.9 I seek the advice of other people in making an important decisions.	4.00	4.10	4.05	Highly Empowered
1.10 When I am under pressure, I will not decide.	3.90	3.80	3.85	Highly Empowered
1.11 I make decision for the development of the school.	4.65	4.60	4.63	Too highly empowered
1.12 I consider various factors in making decision.	4.20	4.20	4.20	Highly Empowered

1.13 I avoid making important decisions until the pressure is on.	3.95	4.00	3.98	Highly Empowered
1.14 I make good and timely decisions, and ensure that they are executed.	4.00	4.10	4.05	Highly Empowered
1.15 I make decision based on reliable sources.	4.55	4.25	4.40	Highly Empowered
Average Mean	4.15	4.11	4.13	Highly Empowered

E. Administrative Empowerment in Decision making according to School Head's Profile

A. According to Gender

Table 5 illustrates the significant difference on administrative empowerment in terms of decision making. It was found that the sig. value is 4.74 and above the 0.05 alpha level.

Table 5.: Administrative Empowerment in Decision Making as to Gender

Administrative Empowerment	Gender of School Heads	N	Mean Diff.	Sig.	Decision	Interpretation
Decision-Making as perceived by administrators	Male	11	.157	.474	Ho is Accepted	No Significant Difference
	Female	9				

B. According to Age

Table 6 expounds the significant difference on administrative empowerment in terms of decision making according to administrators' age. It was found that the sig. value is .04 and below the 0.05 alpha level.

Table 6: Administrative Empowerment in Decision Making according to Age

Administrative Empowerment		Sum of Squares	Sig	Decision	Sig.
Decision making as perceived by administrators	Between Groups	1.645	.04	Ho is Rejected	There is Significant Difference
	Within Groups	2.624			

C. According to Educational Qualification

Table 7 Illustrates the significant difference on administrative empowerment in terms of decision making according to administrators' educational qualifications. It was found that the sig. value is .825 and above the 0.05 alpha level.

Table 7: Administrative Empowerment in Decision making as to Educational Qualification

Administrative Empowerment		Sum of Squares	Sig	Decision Interpretation		
Decision-making as perceived by administrators	Between Groups	.228	.825	Ho is Accepted	No Significant Difference	is
	Within Groups	4.041				
	Total	4.269				

D. According to Educational Length of Service

Table 8 presents the significant difference on administrative empowerment in terms of decision making, formulation and implementation of school policies, and instructional planning according to administrators' length of service. It was revealed that the Sig. values is .016 and above the 0.05 alpha level.

Table 8. Administrative Empowerment in Decision making as to Length of Service.

Administrative Empowerment		Sum of Squares	Sig	Decision Interpretation		
Decision-making as perceived by administrators	Between Groups	1.253	.126	Ho is Accepted	No Significant Difference	is
	Within Groups	3.016				
	Total	4.269				

E. According to Administrators' and Teachers' Ratings

Table 8 presents the significant difference on administrative empowerment in terms of decision making according to administrators' and Teachers' ratings. The sig value is .000 and below the 0.05 level of significance.

Table 8 : Administrative Empowerment in Decision making according to Raters

Administrative Empowerment	Raters	Mean Difference	Sig. (two tailed)	Decision Interpretation		
Decision-Making	Administrators	4.15	.000	Reject Ho	There is significant Difference	is
	Teachers	4.11				

DISCUSSION

This section exposes the profile of the respondents, the administrative empowerments of the school heads in terms of decision making, the difference of decision making according to profile and according administrator's rating and teachers' rating.

A. Profile of the Respondents

Gleaning from the Table 1, 11 (55%) of the school heads were male and only 9 (45%) were female. This data suggests that the number of male school heads in Pangutaran District is slightly higher than the female. In terms of age, majority 7 (35%) of the school heads of Pangutaran District were belonging to an age bracket of 56-65 years old; while, 6 (30%) of them were at 36-45 years old. Meanwhile, 5 (25%) of them were belonging to 46-55 years old. And only 2 (10%) of them were at 25-35 years old. Hence, it can be deduced that most the school heads of Pangutaran District were almost at the old age already and have experience enough in running the school institutions.

As to their length of service, majority 8 (40%) of the school heads were working from 21-30 years already. While 6 (30%) of them were in the service for about 11-20 years. Further, 4 (20%) were in the profession for 31-40 years; and only 2 (10%) have been in the service for and below. This finding denotes that most of the school heads were already experienced enough to handle challenges and other educational crises while managing the educational institutions.

In terms of administrators' educational qualifications, majority 10 (50%) of them have already finished their master's degree; While 4 (20 %) of the school heads were having their doctoral units; 3 (15%) of them were having master's units; and also, only 3 (15%) have doctoral degree.

The findings revealed that there were lots of school heads who are still pursuing their professional advancement through enrolling in the graduate studies. This implies that elementary schools in Pangutaran District have the greater chance to be at par with other elementary school in the region in terms of educational qualifications of the school heads.

This finding is supported Abdurahman & Omar (2021) in their study on School head's leadership practice and teachers' performance : The case of Omar District, Division of Sulu, Philippines, that 73.2% of the elementary school teachers in Sulu are female and 26.8 percent female. This finding is also supported by Abdurahman (2023) in his study on Job satisfaction and performance of the secondary school teachers in the schools' Division of Sulu, Philippines which states that 72% of all teachers are women, 12% are secondary school principals and 10% are superintendents.

Moreover, this is also corroborated with the study of Abdurahman, et. al (2024) in this study on Exploring the difficulties in teaching Science among intermediate grade teachers in selected schools in MBHTE Sulu, Southern Philippines: basis for program interventions that the majority 130 (72.2%) of the elementary school teachers were female and only 50 (45%) were male. This data implies that the number of female teachers is greater than the male teachers.

B. Administrative Decision Making as Rated by Teachers

Gleaning from Table 4.3, the administrative empowerment in terms of decision making has an average mean of 4.11 from the rating of the teachers which means Highly Empowered. This implies that the school heads of Pangutaran District, MBHTE-Sulu were highly empowered as to decision making.

When taking specifically, they were *Too highly empowered* (mean = 4.60) when making decision for the development of the school. This means that the school heads have greater degree of freedom to decide for the betterment of the school.

Besides, school heads were highly empowered to make decision that suit to their teachers. Likewise, the school heads were *highly empowered* to make decisions by considering various options in terms of specific goal. They too were highly empowered to make decision based on reliable sources; with the consent of the superior; and making sure their decisions are rational. In the same manner, the school heads were highly empowered to make decisions by considering various factors; through logical and systematic way; by seeking advice from other people; and by doing them in good and timely manner and ensuring these decisions were executed promptly. Further, they were highly empowered not to make important decisions when under pressure. Lastly, the school heads were highly empowered to make decision relying on instincts and intuitions.

Accordingly, Decision-making empowerment involves providing employees with the right to make applicable decisions concerning basic workplace issues. For instance, front office personnel may be equipped with decision-making power over what type of office supplies to order and where to purchase them from. Decision should be pertinent to the individual job at hand. The process of training and preparing principals is driven by a characteristics model. Underlying each of the components in the characteristics model is decision preparation and ongoing development.

This finding is supported by Abdurahman & Omar (2021) in their study on School head's leadership practice and teachers' performance: The case of Omar District, Division of Sulu, Philippines, they found that school heads were willingly solicit opinions when they are in doubt and very open for suggestions when it comes to decision making.

C. Administrative Empowerment in Decision Making as Rated by Administrators

Gleaning from Table 3, the administrative empowerment in terms of decision making has an average mean of 4.15 as rated by administrators themselves which means Highly Empowered. This implies that the school heads of Pangutaran District, MBHTE-Sulu were highly empowered as to decision making.

When taking specifically, they were *Too highly empowered* (mean = 4.63) when making decision for the development of the school. This means that the school heads have greater degree of freedom to decide for the betterment of the school.

Further, the school heads were strongly empowered to make decision for the development of the school. Besides, they make decisions based on reliable sources and that would suit their teachers and with the consent and knowledge of their superior. In the

same manner, the school heads were highly empowered to make decisions and ensure its execution; they make decisions in a logical and systematic way and by considering various factors. Additionally, the school heads were highly empowered to make decisions by considering various option in terms of specific goal; By seeking advice of other people; and by avoiding making decision when so much pressure is on. Moreover, the school heads were highly empowered not to make according to their intuitions and instincts.

In the same vein, Hickman, Moore and Torek (2008) discussed the importance of principal support in transforming normal classroom practitioners into school leaders making decisions collectively. "Principals who are dedicated to distributed leadership must foster an environment of trust at all levels by trusting teachers to make sound, well informed decisions about what is best for their students".

D. Administrative Decision Making as Rated by Teachers and Administrators Themselves

Gleaning from Table 4, the administrative empowerment in terms of decision making has an average mean of 4.13 from combined ratings from administrators themselves and the teachers which means Highly Empowered. This implies that the school heads of Pangutaran District, MBHTE-Sulu were highly empowered as to decision making.

When taking specifically, they were Too highly empowered ($m = 4.63$) when making decision for the development of the school. This means that the school heads have greater degree of freedom to decide for the betterment of the school.

Besides, school heads were highly empowered to make decision with the consent and knowledge of their superior. They were also highly empowered to make decision that suit to their teachers; and they were also highly empowered to make decision in a logical and systematic way. In the same way, the school heads were highly empowered to make decisions by considering various options in terms of specific goal; by ensuring its proper execution; and by relying on their instincts and intuitions. Further, they too were highly empowered in terms of making rational decision; by seeking the advice of other people when making important one; and by not deciding when under pressure.

Moreover, the school heads were highly empowered in terms of decision making by considering various factors; by avoiding to make important decisions until the pressure is on; by making good and timely decisions and ensure that they are executed; and by making decision based on reliable sources.

According to Bogler and Nir (2012) empowerment suggests real changes in one's professional expertise, rising autonomy and involvement in decision making processes. Similarly, Bolin (1989) emphasizes that empowerment is participating in decisions about school goals and practicing these decisions in educational field.

E. Administrative Empowerment in Decision Making and Profile of the School Heads

e.1. According to Gender

Gleaning from table 5, it can be deduced that there is no significant difference on the administrative empowerment of the school heads of Pangutaran District in the areas of Decision making as attested by sig value of .474 and was above the .05 alpha level. This implies that the hypothesis which states that “there is no significant difference of administrative empowerment of school heads in terms of decision making is accepted. Therefore, the perception of male and female administrators in on administrative empowerments as to decision making is almost the same.

e.2. According to Age

Based on the Table 6, it can be said that there was significant difference on the administrative empowerment of school heads in Pangutaran District in terms of Decision making as reflected in in the sig value 0. 046 and below the 0.05 alpha level. This means that those administrators belonging 25-35 years of age and 36-45 years old have different perceptions with that of school heads belonging to 56-65 years old.

e.3. According to Educational Qualification

Gleaning from the same table, there was no significant difference could be seen on administrative empowerment in terms of decision-making with sig. value of 0.826; Thus the sig. value is above the 0.05 alpha level. Hence, it can be deduced that the hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference on the administrative empowerment in terms of decision making was hereby accepted. It would mean, regardless of their educational qualification, the perception of the administrators on administrative empowerment in terms of decision making do not vary with each other.

e.4 According to Length of Service

As revealed in Table 8, there was no significant difference could be seen on administrative empowerment in terms of decision making according to the administrator’s length of service with sig. value of .126 and this is above the 0.05 alpha level. Therefore, it can be deduced that the hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference on the administrative empowerment in terms of decision making was hereby accepted. This means that administrators themselves have almost the same perception in terms of administrative empowerment as to decision making regardless of their length of service.

e.5. According to Administrators’ and Teachers’ Rating

Gleaning from Table 8, a significant difference could be seen on administrative empowerment in terms of decision making as to administrators’ and teachers’ rating with sig. value of .000; Hence, the sig value was above the 0.05 alpha level. Therefore, it can be deduced that the hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference on the administrative empowerment in terms of decision making, according to administrators’ and teachers’ ratings” was hereby rejected. This implies that the perception of the school heads of Pangutaran District varies and much higher than the perception of the teachers

in terms of administrative empowerment. This means also that from the view point of the school administrators, they are highly empowered in terms of decision making.

Conclusions

This study sought to investigate the administrative empowerment of the school heads in Pangutaran District, MBHTE-Sulu. On the basis of the findings of the study, the following are the conclusions derived from the investigations.

The majority of the school heads were male, aged from 56-65, most of them were with masters' degree and have been rendering services from 21-30 years in the service.

That the school heads were rated "highly empowered" in terms of decision making, Further, there was no significant difference between male and female on their perspective on the administrative empowerment of School heads' decision making. Likewise, there was a significant difference on the perception of the respondents in terms of age. Meanwhile, there was no significant difference could be gleaned on administrative empowerment on school heads' decision making in terms of educational qualification and length of services. Moreover, there was a significant difference between the perception of the administrators and the teachers as to decision making.

Recommendations

On the basis of the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are hereby forwarded

1. The MBHTE- BARMM may legislate regional policy to help intensify the empowerment of the school principals in the respective divisions.
2. The MBHTE-Sulu may create an avenue for administrator's continuing professional development for school head in both elementary and secondary level.
3. The MBHTE-Sulu must continue strengthen the administrative empowerment of all school heads in the Province of Sulu.
4. Future researchers must delve deeper to conduct a similar study to validate the herein findings of the same.
5. The following research topics are also forwarded as reference for the future researchers:
 - A. "Impact of Administrative Empowerment to Teacher's Performance in MBHTE-
 - B. "Administrative Empowerment vis-à-vis School Development": The Case of MBHTE-Sulu
 - C. "Administrative Empowerment: Its Relationship to Innovative Behavior of School heads in MBHTE-Sulu"

Ethical Considerations

Foremost, the researchers have put the ethical treatment of the participants with utmost priority. Safeguarding the right to privacy of the participants is at major stake.

Anent this, the researchers have sent an informed consent to the respondents which clearly explains the purpose, procedures, potential risks and benefits of the study. In like manner, teachers were also informed of their rights to and not-to participate in the study. They were likewise informed that the researchers have preserved a maximum confidentiality. Furthermore, in respect to the privacy of the respondents, the data collected were actually stored in a secured archive where only the researchers can access. And, anonymization of these data was strictly observed wherein no particular information of the respondents were linked to the study. Moreover, all participants were treated with respect regardless of their diverse perspective and opinions. Finally, the researchers created a safe space for the respondents to give them freedom to share their experiences in line with the objectives of the study.

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